

Natural Language Processing for Text Analysis: Sentiment Analysis

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Abstract— The automatic extraction of positive or negative attitude expressions from text, known as sentiment analysis, has drawn a lot of attention from academics in the last ten years. They hold both favourable and unfavourable opinions on various individuals, groups, locations, occasions, and concepts. It is now possible to start extracting feelings from websites thanks to the tools given by natural language processing and machine learning, coupled with other methods for working with massive amounts of material. In this paper, we discuss some of the difficulties in sentiment extraction, some of the methods used to overcome these difficulties, and our method of sentiment analysis from user feedbacks, which yields results that go beyond just polarity and makes use of those polarities in service profiling and quality. Promising outcomes have demonstrated that the strategy may be improved to address business environment needs using sentiment analysis in websites.

Keywords — Natural Language Processing (NLP), sentiment analysis, POS tagger

I. INTRODUCTION

Natural language processing (NLP) is a fast developing discipline with a lot of potential to address problems in the real world. NLP has attracted a lot of interest recently because of its capacity to improve website user experience. This study examines how different NLP techniques could be used to address practical issues facing the service centre business. The suggested system seeks to provide an avant-garde and user-focused online service centre management system. The study includes sentiment analysis of service centre reviews using NLP, one of the major NLP developments covered. The final objective is to demonstrate how NLP can revolutionise the experience of using virtual services, allowing consumers to save time and make educated decisions. Overall, this study emphasises how NLP has the power to revolutionise the service centre management sector and provides insightful advice for both scholars and practitioners.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

In their article "Sentiment Analysis for e-Services" by Fernando Santos-Sanchez and Andres Mendez-Vazquez [1], the authors examine the exponential growth of new e-services online every year. The majority of them must examine and understand vast amounts of data. However, a lot of them overlook the sentiments and feelings expressed on the website when conducting their analysis. So, by examining the sentimental and emotional content of each page, we proposed a novel system in this work to obtain relevant data from a Web search engine. Given the average sentimental rates in the forums, it is possible to determine how the Web community perceives the product. This information can offer a new

method to determine how the community has reacted to a product. Additionally, by grouping the comparison pages for easy access, this classification makes it possible to identify the best sales options given a specific product and to significantly reduce the time required to find the best options. As a result, we believe that this method is the beginning of a new way to help customers choose the best thing to buy and that it helps us to have a more thorough understanding of how consumers evaluate the suggested products.

They describe sentiment analysis to ascertain the sentiment of the comments and reviews in their study "Integrated Feedback Analysis And Moderation Platform Using Natural Language Processing" by Ambarish Moharil, Shreya Singh, Yash Dravid, Harshal Dharap, and Prof. Vijaykumar Bhanuse [2]. The study discusses the significance of preparing raw data for machine learning classification and natural language processing, covering actions like lemmatization, stemming, and removal of special letters and symbols. The study also explains how two tokenizers, count vectorizer and TF-IDF tokenizer, are used to assess the sentiment of reviews and feedback, as well as how tokenization is utilised to vectorize a particular text corpus. The last section of the paper describes how the TF-IDF calculates the term frequency and inverse frequency of words, as well as how the admin can view the TF-IDF score matrix for terms with a threshold greater than 0.5 to summarise the entire review or feedback in two to three words rather than reading it in its entirety.

The application of sentiment analysis on Twitter data to identify the type of sentiment in tweets is covered by Kusrini and Mochamad Mashuri in their study "Sentiment Analysis In Twitter Using Lexicon Based and Polarity Multiplication" [3]. In order to analyse the substantial amount of data created on Twitter, the essay emphasises the value of text mining and natural language processing techniques. The article also covers the possible uses of sentiment analysis in a variety of fields, including market research, political campaigns, and product reviews. The study emphasises using lexicons and multiplication polarity for sentiment analysis and proposes that lexicon semantics need to be further improved in order to increase accuracy.

III. IMPLEMENTATION

A. Data Pre-processing

Gathering the reviews from the dataset is the first stage. As is common knowledge, it is crucial to process a text before classifying it. The pre-processing and cleanup of superfluous data in the dataset are the main goals of the second stage. First, standardisation of punctuation is done to make sure that writing conventions can be followed. After that, each review has all non-alphabetical characters—such as numbers, emotion letters like smileys, punctuation marks like periods, hyphens, and apostrophes—removed. The review's entire vocabulary is then changed to lowercase letters. Each split word and phrase is then used for additional processing.

B. Sentiment Tokenization

The review text is tokenized in this stage by first dividing it into words and then into sentences (depending on the use of periods). The next phase is typically designed to undertake a morph syntactic analysis once the text has been divided into tokens in order to identify properties, such as its grammatical or lexical category. POS tagging is a term used to describe this study.

C. POS Tagger

A POS tagger is a method of natural language processing that scans text in a particular language as input and assigns POS tags to each word in a phrase, including nouns, verbs, adjectives, and other words. Adjective, noun, verb, pronoun, adverb, preposition, conjunction, and interjection are the eight POS in the English language. Stanford POS was used as the POS tagger in this study. Instead of merely eight, the tagger is able to provide 36 distinct tags that can recognise more intricate syntactic components. The term scores in the classification process can be calculated using POS tags, which show how informative a word is.

D. Negation

In a sentence, negation reverses the polarity of the already paired terms. Negation words that change the polarity of the word they are used with, like "not," "can't," and "don't," include these three. For instance, a positive word will always⁴ become negative when it is combined with a negation word. In contrast, a negation word changes a negative word into a positive term. The negative words must therefore be properly handled in a sentiment categorization. This procedure modified the work done by Pang et al.

E. Term Score

This procedure creates a set of sentiment scores after taking the review-corresponding feature vector, which reflects the POS. The sentiment lexicon, the most important resource for the majority of SA approaches, is used to provide a term score to each sentiment-carrying word inside the input review. SentiWordNet was created for this study to target the synsets as the primary WordNet component according to the "positive," "negative," and "neutral" notation of each sunset.

F. Sentiment Classification

The feature set that is chosen to represent a user's opinion is what determines how sentiment is classified. Each review includes a range of subjective terms in a different order. The

feature set that was chosen includes a variety of grammatical terms. This work uses an unsupervised lexicon-based technique for sentiment categorization. The difference between the sums of review R's positive and negative phrase scores is used to determine its sentiment classification.

IV. METHOD OF IMPLEMENTATION

A. Data Pre-processing

The reviews from the dataset are gathered as part of the data preparation. As is common knowledge, it is crucial to process a text before classifying it. The pre-processing and cleanup of superfluous data in the dataset are the main goals of the second stage. First, standardisation of punctuation is done to make sure that writing conventions can be followed. After that, each review has all non-alphabetical characters—such as numbers, emotion letters like smileys, punctuation marks like periods, hyphens, and apostrophes—removed. The review's entire vocabulary is then changed to lowercase letters. Each split word and phrase is then used for additional processing.

1. Sentiment Tokenization

The review text is tokenized in this stage by first dividing it into words and then into sentences (depending on the use of periods).

2. POS Tagger

A POS tagger is a method of natural language processing that scans text in a particular language as input and assigns POS tags to each word in a phrase, including nouns, verbs, adjectives, and other words. Adjective, noun, verb, pronoun, adverb, preposition, conjunction, and interjection are the eight POS in the English language. Stanford POS was used as the POS tagger in this study.

3. Negation

Each sentence in the review is examined for the presence of a list of negation words as part of the negation handling process. If a negation word is discovered, a negation procedure is used; it is regarded as a set of negation words with the following definitions.

4. Term Score

This procedure creates a set of sentiment scores after taking the review-corresponding feature vector, which reflects the POS. The sentiment lexicon, the most important resource for the majority of SA approaches, is used to provide a term score to each sentiment-carrying word inside the input review.

B. Feature Selection

The main objective of this work is feature extraction from various POS (adjectives, adverbs, verbs, and nouns). A tokenized tag with a word score assigned to it is given to the feature selection process for each feature. Then, each tag feature is chosen independently in order to compare how well each POS tag affects sentiment polarity. A new feature set is created by combining sets of the greatest POS tags.

1. Sentiment Classification

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2. Dataset and Evaluation Matrices

The dataset was cleaned and pre-processed from its raw state. For instance, the HTML parser was used to get rid of HTML tags. In addition, all numerals and punctuation marks were removed. On a dataset, experiments were carried out. The benchmark dataset known as the experimental dataset comprises of many areas.

V. RESULT

We contrasted our strategy with the lexicon-based classifier in order to assess how well our suggested strategies performed. The first baseline is based on the idea that the polarity of a text may be calculated by adding the individual polarity values of each word or phrase used in the text. Each term is associated with numerical scores that indicate the sentiment of a text, including both positive and negative sentiment. Positive overall polarity is stated to exist in a text if the sum of positive word polarities exceeds the amount of negative word polarities. Otherwise, the text's overall polarity is deemed negative. To measure the sentiment polarity of a text, the second baseline counts the amount of positive and negative word scores. According to this method, the text's overall polarity is deemed positive if the number of positive words outnumbers the number of negative ones. Otherwise, the text's overall polarity is regarded as negative.

TABLE I. POSITIVE REVIEW ANALYSIS

<i>Service Centers</i>	<i>Polarity</i>
Tagbikers	7
Bandidose	5
Shutter	6
Yamaha	1

TABLE II. NEGATIVE REVIEW ANALYSIS

<i>Service Centers</i>	<i>Polarity</i>
Tagbikers	1
Bandidose	4
Shutter	0

VI. CONCLUSION

The capacity of Natural Language Processing (NLP) to address problems in the actual world has attracted a lot of interest recently. The potential of NLP to improve the customer experience in online service centre management is examined in this research by utilising a variety of NLP techniques. With the help of the suggested system, an innovative and user-centered online service centre management solution that can efficiently process and assess service behaviours will be created. The article discusses important developments in NLP, such as sentiment analysis of service centre reviews using NLP. The final objective is to

demonstrate how NLP has the ability to revolutionise the virtual servicing experience and empower users to make time- efficient decisions.

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